

Rahu- Completion of Circle

32 Comments / English Blogs / By Deepanshu Giri

ॐ गुरुवे नमः

I pray to the creator of light, I pray to the one who has given me consciousness to understand the cosmos. I hope some portion of this article helps you in understanding the light inside you.

When there is light in one part of the world, darkness rules the other half to give peaceful sleep to half of the world, Similarly, when there is light for the Soul from where the soul originates, there is also a termination of this soul where soul completes its journey that is Rahu.

If you have not read the last article on Source and Sink in astrology then it's time that you should read the article [Understanding Conjunction in Vedic Astrology – Lunar Astro Vedic Academy](#).

The energy of life travels from Sun to Rahu from the light source of the big bang to the blackhole of the universe, Why do you need Blackhole? Ketu is considered Mokshkaraka but what about Rahu, these two are the part of same entity, you can either go out of this universe via Rahu or Ketu.

Some combinations are made for this world and some are made for your future travel or past birth and these combinations only act as limiting barriers in which your life will operate Sun Rahu is one of the Sun is a source from where you are originating and Rahu is where you need to terminate, this is a combination of afterlife result.

Sun Mercury is the combination of this world which will help you most in day-to-day behaviour as Mercury is a planet of relations and especially in 6th/12th/1st/5th- this combination will work showing your energy is used only to run the day to day activities and you are very sharp in the understanding of this world, while Sun Rahu shows now your understanding will be of another world and all this intelligence and light will be used afterlife.

Sun-Mars combination shows, Your ability in giving birth to various things such as in the 2nd house then it will be about generating money at a fast speed or let us say burning Shukra at a fast speed and this is why it also shows the short life of a spouse or married life problems.

Sun Jupiter shows your energy and light will be used for higher understanding and knowledge and this will make native problem solver authority especially when Jupiter is combusted by Sun, It shows high ranking official especially when the combination is happening in 1/7/12/9/4 house.

This is to terminate the karma as no future will be given out to this planet. Rahu which happens to be on one end – A black hole and this shows the final birth of native as native is born to complete the remaining karma of the soul. Not only Sun Rahu – Rahu 5th house is putradosh which means as there is no karma which natives can carry in the future there is why a black hole is created in the 5th.

When placed in a lagna, this shows karma related to the physical body will be over as when Rahu is in a lagna, this is the last birth of the native to experience all the body disfigurement and pains. To come and leave earth will be painful and both times you will be helpless, that is why stay humble. (keep head down and be humble).

When placed with Sun this shows the will to live comes down as natives experience everything in life, If you see a chart of saint Maharishi Mahesh Yogi with Sun Rahu combination, he taught people how to meditate as being in the 12th house he was able to teach people the benefit of being in another world.

Rahu is a connection to another world and when combine with an active state there are times when you will find these natives lost in themselves in their own process and methods as they are connected to another world, Even in work this is not the combination to be the number one but to be in a shadow to perform like invisible person, like strategist.

When Venus Rahu combination happens in a chart, this shows the karma related to Shukra will be completed in this lifetime as well as native will have experiences related to family which will eventually lead to dissatisfaction that the native will not be able to say this to anyone that how closed one's are using the native but still complete the karma.

Astrologers have a habit of either glorifying a combination or downplaying a combination but in reality, It is about understanding the energy of a combination and how you reach it purely your understanding of life. I have met people with Jupiter in lagna and still frauds and Rahu in Lagna and most genuine people they are, There is a lot which depends on your own personality, conditioning and behaviours. Every time, I think I have understood 1% of Jyotish, I remember how small I am and how every day I get some portion of wisdom from the sky.

Here is a link to the Happiness series- Predictive 2 to understand such concepts in detail.

[Happiness Series Live Class](#) | [Pending Karma Course](#) | [Saturday](#) | [Hindi – Lunar-Astro](#)
([lunarastro.com](#)).

Link for Research Classes Starting 15th July – <https://lunarastro.com/ninja-forms/44d5ok>

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32 thoughts on “Rahu- Completion of Circle”

PRAVEEN KUMAR

18 JUNE 2023 AT 07:21

Thank you Deepansuji

Such an wonderful article .their must be combination or some clue that one day I am sure you will decode it how human enter to another plane leaving earth plane.one thing is very clear Lord rahu will make it or break it.

Edit

Reply

DILIP NARAYANA SWAMY

18 JUNE 2023 AT 08:17

Jai Shri Radhe 🙏🙏🙏

What a breakthrough analysis and deeper philosophy explained with such simplicity!!

Biggest questions are getting solved within the charts with this beautiful explanation. Especially to identify the purpose of the journey, on the karmic plane!

Thank you so much Sirji 🙏